

Screening of elite rice strains and varieties for bacterial blight (BB) resistance

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BB, caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, is a major rice disease in the Tarai region of western Uttar Pradesh, and incidence is increasing throughout the state. In 1983 kharif, 6 All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) variety trials—uniform varietal trials 1, 2, and 3; preliminary variety trials 2 and 3; and Aromatic Slender Grain Varietal Trial (ASGVT), with 15, 22, 30, 64, 64, and 22 entries, were evaluated for BB incidence in replicated trials at the Crop Research Center of G. B. Pant University. Environmental conditions favored natural disease development and BB incidence was very high. Disease reaction was recorded at 50% flowering stage on a 0-9 scale.

Of 317 entries evaluated, 37 showed resistant reaction (3) (see table). The resistant entries were evaluated under

Rice varieties with field resistance to BB at Pantnagar in 1983 kharif.

Experiment	Varieties or elite strains with BB resistance
UVT 1	RP1670-1418-2205-1582 (IET7613), Govind, Cauvery
UVT 2	CR200-788-3 (IET6775), CR167-7 (IET4507), AD9246 (IET6985), OR173-1-1 (IET7179), RP1036-35-2-5-1-1 (IET7230), PR103 (IET7267), Pusa 205-15-1 (IET7279), CR163-CRRD-50 (IET780), CR75-93 Mut. 11-4 (IET7713)
UVT 3	IR54 (IET7296), or 147-1-137 (IET7174), Pant Dhan 4
PVT 2	RP1575-636-6-1 (IET8713), RP1775-243-719-681 (IET8718), NDR302 (IET8054), KR10-47 (IET8055), RAU4056-53-5, (IET8056), or 79-21 (IET5975), SKL 6 (IET7169), or 131-5-8 (IET7433), HPU804 (IET7500), BPT1235 (IET8040), BIET263 RAU49 (IET8044), UPR79-164 (IET8048), UPR254-21-1-1 (IET8049), UPR103-44-2 (IET8050), NDR301 (IET8053), NSRP11 Late (IET8700), BAU4090-1 (IET8702), UPR81-44 (IET8709), BK670 (IET8711), NRL 326-3 (IET8713), Rasi, Prasad
PVT 3	Pant Dhan 4

artificial epiphytotic conditions in 1984 kharif using standard clipping for disease inoculation. Under heavy BB pressure, all entries had susceptible reaction, scoring between 7 and 9. Results show that presently available elite materials in AICRIP trials have a low level of BB resistance. Therefore, there is a need to increase the level of resistance by incorporating new resistance genes into elite lines to combine stability with higher yields. DV85 and BJ1, which showed resistance at Pantnagar under artificial epiphytotic conditions, might be used as donors. □

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Field screening of rice cultivars for resistance to black bug *Scotinophara coarctata*

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The first reported black bug outbreak in the Philippines was in Bonobono, Bataraza, southern Palawan, in 1982. Rices were screened for black bug resistance in a farmer field at Maasin, Brookes Point, in Jul-Dec 1983.

Three hundred rice breeding lines were sown in thermo cups and transplanted in caged plots at 15 test entries/plot and 10 hills/entry, 2-3 seedlings/hill. Water was maintained 3-5 cm deep for 20 d after

transplanting (DT). Field-collected black bug adults were introduced 20 DT at 5 bugs/hill (750 black bugs/test cage plot). Plot size was 1.5 × 3 m. Immediately after infestation, the field was drained, which favored black bug survival. The field remained saturated throughout the experiment.

Of the 300 rices screened, 20 were selected based on damage reaction. They were retested in the same field in Jan-May 1984 with 35 black bug adults/hill and treatments in 4 replications. The number of black bugs in 5 randomly chosen hills/test entry was recorded 20 d after infestation (DAI). Plant damage was rated at 20, 40, and 60 DAI based on the following scale:

Rating	Description
0	No damage.
1	Wilting of youngest leaf.
3	Wilting of youngest leaf and partial yellowing of the first, second, and third older leaves.
5	Wilting of more than two leaves and pronounced yellowing of the first, second, and third older leaves.
7	More than half the plants wilting or dead and remaining plants severely stunted.
9	All plants dead or bugburned.

Reaction of selected breeding lines to the black bug,^a Palawan, Philippines in 1984 dry season.

Breeding line ^b	Black bugs (no./hill) 20 DAI	Plant damage at indicated DAI		
		20	40	60
IR13149-71-3-2	149 abc	3.5 a	4.0 a	5.0 a
IR10781-75-3-2-2	133 ab	4.0 b	4.0 a	5.5 a
IR18350-175-2-3	155 abc	3.5 a	5.5 ab	7.5 ab
BG379-1	200 c	3.5 a	5.5 ab	8.0 b
IR19661-23-3-2-2	126 ab	5.0 bc	5.5 ab	8.0 b
IR12721-24-3-1	173 bc	5.0 bc	6.5 abcd	8.0 b
BW295-4	129 ab	4.5 bc	7.5 cdef	8.0 b
BR316-15-4-4-1	131 ab	5.5 bcd	6.0 abc	8.5 b
BR445-60-1b	162 bc	5.0 bc	7.0 bcdef	8.5 b
IR13240-108-2-2-3	134 ab	6.0 c	7.0 bcdef	8.5 b
IR25774-3-1-1	169 bc	4.5 bc	7.0 bcdef	8.5 b
IR36 (check)	167 bc	5.5 bcd	7.0 bcdef	8.5 b
Tjeremas (purple base)	109 ab	7.0 d	8.0 def	8.5 b
BG400-1	134 ab	5.5 bcd	8.5 g	9.0 c
B2791b-Mr-257-3-2	145 abc	4.5 bc	6.5 abcd	9.0 c
B3981c-Pn-200-2-2	97 a	7.0 d	8.5 g	9.0 c
Cul. 6914	170 bc	5.0 bc	8.5 g	9.0 c
IR12979-24-1	133 ab	5.5 bcd	7.0 bcdef	9.0 c
IR13415-9-3	161 bc	5.0 bc	7.0 bcdef	9.0 c
C1754-5	121 ab	5.5 bcd	7.5 cdef	9.0 c
IR31917-31-3-2	148 abc	5.5 bcd	8.0 def	9.0 c
Tjeremas (green base - local check)	203 c	5.0 bc	7.5 cdef	9.0 c

^a Av of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. ^b Breeding lines selected from the 300 test entries screened in Jul-Dec 1983.

The first 5 test entries tolerated high black bug population at 40 DAI (see table). However, IR13149-71-3-2 and IR10781-75-3-2-2 were the only entries that survived to 60 DAI. IR10781-75-3-2-2, which matures in 131 d, yielded 7 t/ha in 1980 dry season, is resistant to brown planthopper biotypes 1 and 3, and moderately resistant to green leafhopper. The two most resistant lines are being tested for yield under black bug infestation in Palawan. □

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Evaluation of germplasm accessions for green leafhopper (GLH) resistance

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From the IRRI germplasm collection, 204 GLH accessions with resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens*, brown planthopper, whitebacked planthopper, or leafhopper were evaluated for resistance to *N. nigropictus* (Stål) and *N. virescens* (Distant). Separate 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes for each GLH species were used with IR29 as the resistant check and Nira as the susceptible check. Seven days after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 15-20 per entry and infested with 4-5 3d-instar nymphs per seedling. When Nira seedlings died, entries were rated for damage using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale.

Sixty-five entries scored 0-5 for *N. nigropictus* and 105 for *N. virescens*. The entries were further evaluated in three replications. Susceptible entries (scores 6-9) were rejected.

Reactions to both GLH species were similar for many varieties. Fifty-one (25%)

Damage ratings of rice cultivars in seedbox screening for resistance to *N. nigropictus* and *N. virescens*, IRRI, 1983-84.

Cultivar	IRRI accession number	Origin	Damage rating ^a (grade 0-9)	
			<i>N. nigropictus</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>
Resistant to <i>N. nigropictus</i> and <i>N. virescens</i>				
Ari	25830	Bangladesh	3.7	2.4
Ashni	25831	Bangladesh	3.7	2.3
Aus Jhari	25833	Bangladesh	3.7	3.0
Bathuri	25838	Bangladesh	3.7	3.7
Chamka	25844	Bangladesh	3.0	3.7
Chiknal	25848	Bangladesh	3.0	3.0
Dhalashaita	25851	Bangladesh	2.3	3.0
Garia	25854	Bangladesh	1.3	2.3
Gungur Murali	25858	Bangladesh	3.0	3.0
Hasha	25861	Bangladesh	3.7	2.3
Hijolee	25862	Bangladesh	1.0	2.3
Pankhiraj	25911	Bangladesh	3.7	1.7
Terabali	25926	Bangladesh	3.7	1.7
Pahari Balam	31904	Bangladesh	3.0	3.7
D 59-6	33045	Bangladesh	3.0	3.0
Lalmoti	37522	Bangladesh	3.7	1.7
Kalimekri 77-5	37649	Bangladesh	3.7	3.0
Bow Pagal	43796	Bangladesh	3.0	3.0
Chakulia	43798	Bangladesh	3.7	3.0
Molica	43925	Bangladesh	3.0	3.0
Hnanwa Phingauk	4142	Burma	3.7	3.7
ASD7	6303	India	3.7	2.3
Shatika	35150	India	3.7	3.0
ARC14960	43034	India	3.0	3.0
Hassan Tareme	32311	Iran	3.7	3.0
Gadur	16246	Nepal	3.7	3.0
IR2034-289-1-1-1	32684	Philippines	3.7	3.0
Sulai	8908	Sri Lanka	1.7	1.7
Chianung Sen 11	26955	Taiwan	3.0	3.0